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D2.1 - digiNEB.eu web platform, Rel. 1.0

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Glossary of terms

Item	Description
CA	Consortium Agreement
DEP	Digital Europe Programme
DMS	Document Management System
DTPC	Deputy Technical Project Coordinator
EAG	External Advisory Group
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
FACL	Financial & Administrative Coordinator Leader
GA	Grant Agreement
KOM	Kick-off meeting
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
NEB	New European Bauhaus
PMB	Project Management Board
The Consortium	All the Project Partners, viz. TU DELFT + Trust-IT + COMMpla + EAAE + ICF + IW
The Project Beneficiaries	The signatory Partners of the Grant Agreement, viz. TU DELFT + Trust-IT + EAAE + ICF + IW
TL	Task Leader
TPC	Technical Project Coordinator
TWG	Technical Working Group
UI	User Interface
UX	User Experience
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader

Keywords

Website; Web platform; New European Bauhaus; UX; UI; Digital Toolkit, Observatory; eLearning Platform.

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Executive Summary

This document summarises the current characteristics of the digiNEB.eu web platform, which has been designed and developed by Trust-IT. The website has been (silently) launched on 10 October 2022 and it has been progressively evolved since, until the version reported here, Release 1.0.

While it is intended that the website will be continuously evolved and populated from the content point of view, two additional technical releases of the digiNEB.eu platform are planned along the overall 24-month project duration: Rel. 2.0 will be officially launched in Month 09 (June 2023) and Rel. 3.0 in Month 18 (March 2024).

The main purpose of the digiNEB.eu platform is to technically support the development of a digital ecosystem for the New European Bauhaus. The website is also the project's communication hub and main channel to engage with targeted stakeholders and turn them into users and active members of the community in coordination with other communication channels and engagement mechanisms of the NEB environment. The website provides core content and messages to inform relevant stakeholders about the project, disseminate relevant results and offer them the opportunity to access NEB digital solutions.

The website is SEO-driven, follows UX and UI principles, and provides support to a series of other connected tasks, in WP2, WP3, WP4, and also WP5. Finally, it supports the Consortium in complying with the GDPR and the Data Management Plan (deliverable D1.2) in general, and it is set-up to allow performance assessment and web analytics monitoring.

Table of Contents

1. MAIN FEATURES OF THE DIGINEB.EU WEB PLATFORM	6
2. EVOLUTION PATH	7
3. WORKFLOW	9
3.1. WEBSITE ROLES	9
3.2. WIREFLOWS AND WIREFRAMES	10
4. TECHNICAL DETAILS	13
4.1. TERMS OF USE FOR THE DIGITAL SOLUTIONS PUBLISHED IN THE DIGITAL TOOLKIT.....	14
5. WEBSITE MAINTENANCE	15
5.1. MAINTENANCE TEAM	15
5.2. ADMINISTRATION TEAM.....	15
5.3. MONITORING	15
5.4. HOSTING	15
6. DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN AND ETHICS	17
6.1. PRIVACY	17
6.2. INVOLVEMENT OF EXTERNAL USERS	17
6.3. EVENT MANAGEMENT.....	17
6.4. RETENTION PERIOD OF PERSONAL DATA	18
7. CONCLUSIONS	19
8. REFERENCES	20

List of Figures

FIGURE 1 - SELECTED PRINT SCREENS OF THE DIGINEB.EU WEBSITE AS OF NOVEMBER 2022.....	7
FIGURE 2 - WEBSITE CREATION INTERNAL PROCESS.....	9
FIGURE 3 - WEBSITE MOCK-UP (HOMEPAGE, 1ST DRAFT)	11
FIGURE 4 - WEBSITE MOCK-UP (HOMEPAGE, FINAL RELEASE)	12

List of Tables

TABLE 1 - EVOLUTION OF THE WEBSITE	8
TABLE 2 - WEBSITE ROLES.....	9
TABLE 3 - MAIN TECHNICAL FEATURES	13

1. Main features of the digineb.eu web platform

As part of its 24-month timeline, the digiNEB.eu project has designed and delivered a public website in the form of a functional website already in M1 (October 2022) to present and support the main project's activities.

The main purpose of the website is to support all the project's digital processes. It is also the project's communication hub and main channel to engage target stakeholders and turn them into users and active members of the community in coordination with other communication channels and engagement mechanisms. The website provides core content and messages to inform relevant stakeholders about the project and disseminate relevant results for both digiNEB.eu and the overall NEB community.

To achieve this a set of functionalities available on the website intertwine with and support several other activities and tasks of the project.

More specifically, the website offers the following macro-functionalities:

- **Communications hub:** The platform is envisaged to play a central role as an engagement and communication tool for the whole ecosystem. This will be reached through a progressive continuous improvement of the features and services offered, following UX principles and with carefully designed content and messages which will evolve to reflect the progress of the project (see more in section 2.6). This directly supports Task 5.1 (dissemination and communication) and Task 4.1 (stakeholder engagement).
- **Pool of digital solutions:** The digiNEB.eu website will provide access to 200+ digital solutions that can be adopted by the NEB ecosystem through the **Digital Toolkit**. This will be a central element of the entire project, in that it is the true gateway of the NEB community to practical digital solutions enabling implementation of the NEB goals.
- Moreover, the website will host an **Observatory** on the NEB digital ecosystem. This will include the Technical Working Groups (see next element) and a complete collection of EU-funded initiatives related to the New European Bauhaus environment to raise awareness around NEB initiatives and encourage the creation of collaborative opportunities (the so-called "best practices").
- **Technical Working Groups:** The digiNEB.eu website will show the work performed by four thematic TWG (Design and Architecture, Production and Construction, Verticals, and Community and Sustainability). Each TWG brings together top-class experts of the NEB digital ecosystem to stimulate discussions and share best practices that are collected to provide strategic policy recommendations.
- **eLearning courses:** The platform will also provide access to an online catalogue of initiatives and digital solutions that include best practices and training materials. The elearning courses stimulate knowledge sharing and are freely accessible on the digiNEB.eu platform.
- **Early Adopters Network:** The website will also act as one of the main instruments to recruit ambassadors of the digiNEB.eu project who will become early adopters of the digital solutions provided by the project, help identify gaps in the NEB digital ecosystem and find solutions to address them. The Early Adopters will help to increase the visibility of digiNEB.eu throughout the NEB community and vice versa.

Each of those macro-functionalities will eventually translate into an "**asset**" of digiNEB.eu, namely a feature that will be leveraged by the project to achieve its goals and create impact.

2. Evolution path

The development of the digineb.eu web platform follows three main iterations in M01, M09, and M18. In parallel to the website evolution, the eLearning courses platform will be also created and updated through three iterations in M06, M12 and M18, which will be described in D3.3 “Transferring innovation best practices” under WP3.

The first version of the website was published on 10 October 2022. The first release is a functioning website that contains the following main elements:

1. Presentation of the digiNEB.eu initiative and its direct role of support to the NEB initiative;
2. Provisioning of calls to action for interested stakeholders, e.g. to join the Early Adopters network of digiNEB.eu, or submit a proposal to be included in the Observatory;
3. Registration to the project newsletter and therefore initiate the community building activity;
4. News & events area about the NEB ecosystem, with a special focus on events organised or attended by the digiNEB.eu team.

Overall, the digiNEB.eu website also establishes the visual identity of the project. The website is accessible at <https://digiNEB.eu/> and some selected print screens of the landing page released in M01 are visible below.

Figure 1 - Selected print screens of the digiNEB.eu website as of November 2022

In the second and third releases of the website (Rel. 2.0 and Rel. 3.0), the platform will be enriched with digital content beneficial for the NEB community that will be integrated into the Digital Toolkit, Observatory and eLearning courses. An additional page that showcases who the selected Early Adopters are will be included in the next releases of the website as summarised in the table below.

Release	Expected main features	Due date
Rel. 1.0	<p>Initial web presence:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Project’s description, including objectives and target services ● Webform for sounding out Early Adopters ● First release of the Digital Toolkit 	M01 (Oct 2022)
Rel. 2.0	<p>Intermediate version of the website with enhanced digital content:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● First release of the Observatory (the consolidated version arising from the early release distributed as part of Rel. 1.1, in late December 2022) ● Launch of the TWG pages (expected in January 2023, as part of Rel. 1.2) ● First release of the eLearning catalogue (expected in M06, March 2023) ● Showcase of the digiNEB.eu Early Adopters 	M09 (Jun 2023)
Rel. 3.0	<p>Final version of the website that highlights the main achieved results:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● final release of the Digital Toolkit ● final release of the Observatory ● final release of the eLearning courses ● publication of the digiNEB.eu Roadmap ● policy recommendations coming from the TWG pages 	M18 (Mar 2024)

Table 1 - Evolution of the website

3. Workflow

At every website iteration, a structured process is followed within Trust-IT and COMMpla to guarantee the best results, as displayed in **Figure 2**. The marketing team provides a first draft of the website structure and looks based on the main project goals, following UX design principles. The graphic team applies their experience to elaborate a visually attractive mockup, while the technical team is involved in the later implementation and testing phases where the process goes back to the marketing team for feedback. In the mock-up phases the tool FIGMA is used to support interactions between the various teams.

Figure 2 - Website creation internal process

3.1. Website Roles

The website offers the opportunity to its users to create an account and include content online. The main roles that can be assigned on the digiNEB.eu platform are listed in Table 2 and further detailed in the paragraphs below. The **personas and user journeys** established for all the relevant users will be further detailed in deliverable D2.2, documenting Rel. 2.0 of the web platform.

Persona	Profile	Privileges (increasing)
Anonymous visitor	No profile	Navigation
Community Member	Validated login & password	Proposes content for publication
Contributor	Trusted community member	Publishes in the Technical Working Groups, in the Early Adopters area, the Success Stories or in the Digital Toolkit
Moderator	Member of the digiNEB.eu Consortium	Accesses as editor to the CMS of the web platform
Superuser	Selected members of the Trust-IT+COMMpla team	Manages the root password of the web platform

Table 2 - Website Roles

The **Anonymous visitor** is a user interested by the content published on the digiNEB.eu website and, for this reason, visits it regularly or sporadically. This type of user is just interested in getting to know the latest news, events, or digital solutions published on the digiNEB.eu website, but is not interested in publishing content online. We target over 50,000 unique visitors to digineb.eu by the end of the project.

The **Community member** is a user that has created an account on the digiNEB.eu website and has been validated by the generation of a login and password. This user proposes new content to be published on the website, which is checked and validated by Moderators and Superusers.

The **Contributor** is a trusted user that regularly publishes content in the Observatory or Digital Toolkit sections. The Contributor is a Community member that has been upgraded thanks to the quality of content proposed to be published on the website. We expect more than 100 Contributors to be active during the project.

The **Moderator** is a member of the digiNEB.eu team that accesses the CMS of the web platform, and can autonomously publish or edit content online. Around 20 people are expected to play the active role of Moderator. They will be either digineb.eu Consortium Partners or people delegated by them, e.g. EAG members or TWG leaders.

The **Superusers** are a group of selected people among the Trust-IT + COMMpla team, i.e. the project partners responsible for the development of the digiNEB.eu website. This group of experienced people is responsible to assign roles and responsibilities to each type of user and control the type of content published online. Less than 10 people will be Superusers on digineb.eu.

3.2. Wireflows and wireframes

As part of the design and development process of Rel. 1.0, a number of wireflows and wireframes have been developed. A sample of them is represented in the following figures.

As part of the development of the website, the initial requirements have been translated into key concepts to show them in the website. The homepage of the website has to communicate in different ways all the assets of the project, the goal of the project and the main results achieved by the project. In this way, a wireframe has been developed in order to start the building of the website defining the communication message that has been present in the home page.

When the concept has been validated and revised by several iterations, a mockup has been produced a mockup where the key message present in the wireframe has been translated into UI.

Figure 3 - Website mock-up (homepage, 1st draft)

Figure 4 - Website mock-up (homepage, final release)

4. Technical details

The digineb.eu web platform has been developed on the open source content management framework **Drupal** (www.drupal.org). More specifically, the website has been developed in the Drupal 9 version released by the Drupal community.

Drupal has been chosen for its wide spectrum of **functionalities**, supported by a large and qualified communities of developers, including the ability to support different types of users and content (which are specific needs arising from the project's ambitious goals), besides its **security** features.

Drupal natively allows authentication/authorisation security management exploiting different roles, each of them linked to different privileges assigned to a specific group of users. As part of the website management activities, the team managing the web platform will assign different roles and authorisation levels to designated users.

The Digital Toolkit, the Observatory and the eLearning catalogue of courses will be added to the webs platform and will be managed and implemented in Drupal as well, in terms of contents and learning paths suggested to the users. Drupal has also the capability of sharing selected content exposing API endpoints, thus allowing to **reuse** and show content also outside the website, which is well in line with the scope of the NEB initiative.

To give to the users the functionality to bring forward the Technical Working Groups that digiNEB.eu is going to support, the **Flarum** tool (www.flarum.org) has been selected and will be integrated with the Drupal instance of the web platform. Flarum is an OpenSource solution as minimal forum software with high extensibility. It gives the opportunity simply. It is easy to extend using the available extension provided by the Flarum community or writing an owned extension as well. It is written in PHP and Typescript. Drupal uses the API of Flarum to import information about TWG discussion present to Flarum and use them in Drupal to build the Observatory together with other contents already present in Drupal.

It is possible to create an account in digiNEB.eu to contribute actively to the contents of the website. Drupal is used by Identity providers and via Single SignOn, a user can use Flarum without recreating another user by exploiting the authentication/authorization provided by Drupal.

The table below shows the main technical characteristics of the digineb.eu web platform, Rel. 1.0, online at www.digineb.eu.

Item	Details	Notes
CMS	Drupal 9.0	
Database	9.4.8	
Web Server	Apache/2.4.52 (Ubuntu)	
PHP	8.1.2	
Technical Working Groups	Flarum 1.5.0	To be implemented in Rel. 2.0
Digital Toolkit	Drupal view and moderation managed by Workbench	
Observatory	Drupal view and moderation managed by Workbench	To be implemented in late December 2022 (Rel. 1.1)
eLearning platform	Moodle 4	To be implemented in Rel. 2.0
Hosting	AWS (Amazon Web Services)	EC2 instance

Table 3 - Main technical features

4.1. Terms of use for the digital solutions published in the Digital Toolkit

The digiNEB.eu consortium is not responsible for the quality of each of the digital solutions published in the Digital Toolkit (see [here](#) the terms of use of the Digital Toolkit), for which each digital provider retains all rights and obligations towards the end-users.

5. Website maintenance

The website is developed according to SEO-driven principles. All website analytical data will be gathered on a customised dashboard, and tracked monthly using **Google Analytics** to derive detailed statistics on website visitors and users. Monitoring will be in place to track the project KPIs related to website performance and to proactively detect possible problems and implement corrective actions. At the current date, the Google Analytics profile has been set up and the first data about visitors, clicks on call to actions and conversions are being tracked. The main data will be disclosed in the upcoming deliverables and project update reports as a more statistically significant base of data is collected.

5.1. Maintenance team

The website is maintained by the Trust-IT + COMMpla tech team. They routinely perform the following tasks:

- Hosting management;
- Technical maintenance;
- Monitoring.

The maintenance team is also responsible for the design and implementation of all further evolutions of the web platform. Minor releases (e.g., 1.1, 1.2) will be envisaged on a monthly basis, adding new functionalities and/or sections.

5.2. Administration team

The website is administered with a three-tier administration model (hence, the personas defined in Sec. 3.1):

1. **COMMUNITY MEMBERS AND CONTRIBUTORS:** Consortium Partners and Trusted Community Members;
2. **MODERATORS:** The web platform administration team at Trust-IT/COMMpla;
3. **SUPERUSERS:** They are the Trust-IT + COMMpla tech team, administrating the root password of the web platform and in charge of all technical tasks, including updating the security patches of the platform.

5.3. Monitoring

The website instance and the database instance that complete the digiNEB.eu solution are monitored in an automatic way using Uptime Robot (uptimerobot.com) that is a free service to monitor if the website or any other endpoint is up. In case of failure the system sent an email to flag the problem. The notification is sent via email to the Technical team of Trust-IT and via other channels (Internal Technical Communication Channel, private Smartphone of key technical employees of Trust-IT) exploiting 3rd party webhooks.

5.4. Hosting

The website is hosted by Trust-IT on its virtual servers in AWS (Amazon Web Services). The servers are guaranteed by AWS to be in the Ireland region, in order to maintain all the data in the European Union (Respect of GDPR, see also D1.2 “Data management plan”).

The service used to host the website is EC2 (Elastic Compute) able to virtualise a server and use it as a single point of development. This approach is quite spread in deployment guidelines, in order to isolate an environment and base it on the current bare metal capabilities. AWS ensures an excellent service in order to avoid any type of physical accident, disaster recovery, etc. Lastly, the deployment is completely agnostic in terms of availability of resources, physical maintenance and any other aspect to be considered in a typical server farm.

6. Data Management Plan and Ethics

The Consortium is fully aware and respects the ethical rules and standards of Digital Europe, as well as those reflected in the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union and the Data Protection Directive (Directive 95/46/EC). Further, the Consortium has performed an Ethics self-assessment for Project and is fully aware that some of the activities foreseen may fall within the remit of Directive 95/46/EC, as they imply processing of data that could relate to identified or identifiable people. All data management related information is provided in D1.2. Moreover, the full privacy policy is accessible online on the digiNEB.eu website (<https://digiNEB.eu/privacy-policy>).

6.1. Privacy

The website complies with the GDPR (Directive 95/46/EC). The approach followed by digiNEB.eu in the management of personal data reduces the collection and retention of personal and financial data to the absolute minimum. Any data or information collected are held private and strictly confidential. Moreover, data obtained incidentally within the project are handled with confidentiality and managed according to the GDPR.

In any case data acquired via the web portal or during event registration will be used for commercial purposes or shared with any third parties not identified in the [Privacy Policy](#).

Lastly, the terms of use of the website are published [here](#).

6.2. Involvement of external users

Personal information is provided spontaneously by the user with explicit consent and subscription to data processing policies (for example: cookies, navigation data on directly managed portals, session logs) during the registration phase.

The user ID and password are encrypted according to security standards.

The data collected is entered into one or more databases, with password-protected access, within the software infrastructure that manages the platform. This infrastructure is located on virtualized servers located in accordance with the reference regulations (for projects financed by the EC are located in cloud structures in Europe).

Backups are performed on different structures with data encryption.

6.3. Event Management

Enrolment to events will be carried out via the website. Processing for this purpose is generally necessary to allow the DATA CONTROLLER Team to respond to any request to sign up for an event/webinar and, therefore, is necessary for the performance of a contract – Art. 6(1)(b) GDPR.

However, the tracking of event attendance and publication of attendee lists is done on the basis of the Website's interests in managing events and allowing other participants to become aware of persons taking part at the event – Art. 6(1)(f) GDPR.

When signing up for an event via the Website (such as a workshop organised or promoted by the Website), the user will also be asked to provide details such as his/her name, his/her Twitter handle, the dates on which he/she will be attending and other information of relevance for the management of the attendance. His/her payment details (including debit/credit card number and bank account details as needed) will be processed via an external payment gateway.

When signing up for an event via the Website (such as a workshop organised or promoted by the Website), he/she will also be asked whether he/she has any special dietary/access requirements which might need accommodation. This Personal Data may potentially qualify as “health data” or “data revealing his/her religious/philosophical beliefs”, which are special categories of personal data under Art. 9 GDPR, and will be processed only with his/her explicit consent.

6.4. Retention period of personal data

The collected data will be kept for a period of time not exceeding the achievement of the purposes for which they are processed ("conservation limitation principle", art.5, GDPR) and / or for the time necessary for the obligations of law and EC funded projects Rules.

The verification of the obsolescence of the data stored in relation to the purposes for which it was collected is carried out periodically and obsolete data are erased permanently from the website database.

7. Conclusions

This deliverable outlines the main characteristics of the digineb.eu web platform, available at www.digineb.eu since 10 October 2022.

This Release 1.0 of the web platform is developed in Drupal 9 and follows state-of-the-art web criteria, including UI/UX design principles, performing servers on a public cloud with servers in Europe, and maintained by a team performing regular SEO activities.

A further minor release of the platform (Rel. 1.1) will be performed later in the month of December, to bring online the digiNEB.eu Observatory.

Release 2.0 of the digiNEB.eu web platform will be documented in Deliverable D2.2, scheduled for Month 09 (June 2023).

8. References

/1/ [General Data Protection Regulation](#) (GDPR, Regulation EU 2016/679).

/2/ digiNEB.eu Grant Agreement, DIGITAL-CSA number 101083743, funded under the Digital Europe Programme (October 2022).
